

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES, AND PRACTICES OF RESIDENTS TOWARD DOG-RELATED RABIES IN BARANGAY LINAO EAST, TUGUEGARAO CITY

Jericho G. Ferrer

College of Nursing, Public Health and Midwifery, University of La Salette, Inc, Santiago City, Isabela Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17766908>

ABSTRACT

This study assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of residents in Barangay Linao East, Tuguegarao City regarding dog-related rabies. Using a descriptive quantitative design, data were collected from 185 respondents through a structured questionnaire. The results revealed that respondents exhibited a very high level of knowledge on rabies transmission, bite-related injuries, immediate wound care, dog vaccination, observation of biting dogs, and pet owners' responsibilities, with an overall mean of 4.47. Attitudes toward dog-related rabies were highly positive (overall mean = 4.83), indicating strong recognition of preventive measures and compliance with local ordinances. Practices, however, were moderate (overall mean = 3.29), with proper wound care and anti-rabies vaccination being the most consistently performed behaviors, while reliance on traditional remedies or antibiotics was episodic. The analysis of relationships between KAP variables showed a significant positive correlation between knowledge and attitude ($r = 0.634$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that higher awareness fosters proactive attitudes. However, no significant correlations were found between knowledge and practices ($r = 0.127$) or attitude and practices ($r = 0.115$), highlighting a gap between awareness and actual behavioral implementation. Structural barriers such as limited access to treatment centers, financial constraints, and preference for traditional remedies likely contribute to this discrepancy. The study highlights the need for targeted interventions to strengthen practical preventive measures, promote timely reporting, and enhance access to anti-rabies services, thereby ensuring effective rabies prevention and control in the community.

Keywords: *Dog-Bites, Control, Prevention, Pets, Rabies, Transmission*

INTRODUCTION

Rabies is one of the most tenacious and life-threatening zoonotic diseases in the world, especially in places where the dog-mediated transmission still poses a significant health issue to the society. Even though the disease is 100 percent vaccine-preventable, it continues to take the lives of tens of thousands of human beings every year, with most of them being low- and middle-income countries that cannot access timely post-exposure prophylaxis and veterinary treatment. The project has attracted worldwide interest because domestic dogs are the overwhelming source of human rabies infections as revealed by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023), and therefore, the need to prevent dog-bites, ensure responsible dog ownership, and promote community-based education about rabies. Moreover, addressing rabies prevention and control directly supports the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3: Good Health and Well-Being, which aims to end epidemics of neglected tropical diseases such as rabies.

Rabies continues to be a very dangerous menace to the public health of the Philippines and the Republic Act 9482, also referred to as Anti-Rabies Act of 2007 has been enacted to ensure that the mass vaccination of dogs, responsible ownership of pets and increased publicity on the problem are met. However, even though strong legislative frameworks exist, there are still problems on the community level, especially related to irregular adherence to dog vaccination, a lack of knowledge about post-bite guidelines, and weak rabies surveillance in the area.

Research in various contexts repeatedly indicates that Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices (KAP) by the people of the locality have significant effects on the success of the rabies control activity. A study in Indonesia (Devira et al., 2023) emphasized that although most dog owners were aware of the risks of rabies, the misunderstandings about the routes of transmissions and the treatment after being bitten were still widespread. Similarly, in Tanzania, Iddi et al. (2023) noted that the dog owners in general were aware that rabies was lethal, but their preventive measures, including the regular dog vaccination, were not uniform. A study conducted in India, by Sivagurunathan et al. (2021), has shown that insufficient knowledge was a factor linked with poor first-aid procedures in case of animal bites, thus depicting the importance of the sustained public health education.

In addition to personal behaviors, the global health community still promotes the improved measures in the way of dog-mediated rabies eradication. The regional reviews show mixed developments, and some regions seem to achieve a better level of mass dog vaccination and surveillance systems compared to others (Kanda et al., 2022). New methods of vaccination such as agile and reactive mass vaccination in the low- and middle-income communities have demonstrated potential in achieving high coverage levels and containment of outbreak risks by developing and enhancing agile and reactive vaccination (Kandel et al., 2024). Extensive gaps in the literature on African population

also demonstrate that the lack of knowledge and access to veterinary care remains a barrier to the process of eradicating rabies (Woldegeorgis et al., 2023).

These trends are supported by local Philippines evidence. As Tuaño (2025) noted, even though the residents tended to be very positive in the attitude to the prevention of rabies, the lack of practical compliance, including the failure to wash dog-bite bites within the shortest time possible, or the post-exposure prophylaxis tardiness, remained. These results indicate that attitudes are not enough to ensure proper practices, so there is a need to pay more attention to underlying behavioral determinants.

The community is made more vulnerable to rabies because of such knowledge-practice gaps. There is also modulation of the socioeconomic and demographic factors on the attitude and behavior of communities. According to Constantino et al. (2023), the dog-care and bite-prevention practices of poorer households with less access to veterinary services were poor. Such findings indicate that the most effective rabies control should deal with the lack of education and economic limitations simultaneously. In general, cross-national studies reinforce the necessity of strengthening of community knowledge, advantageous attitudes, and improvement of practicable behaviors as part and parcel of effective elimination initiative against rabies. Reinforced KAP interventions will probably reduce bite incidences, fasten early treatment seeking, and eventually lead to eventual elimination of rabies in the long-term perspective.

All these global and regional results bring forward the critical requirement of contextual evaluation on the community level. Knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the residents provide useful information about behavioral patterns that determine the risk of rabies, adherence to the measures of the public health, and reaction to the dog-bite incidents. The targeted interventions would be delivered using such localized information, providing the public health information program and long-term goal of the eradication of rabies.

Considering the current risk of rabies and the need to have a strong community involvement in prevention and control, this paper will assess the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices of the residents of Barangay Linao East, Tuguegarao City on dog bite prevention and control, and thus present an insightful information on a timely basis, needed to enhance the rabies mitigation activities in the area.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of the respondents' knowledge on dog-bites related rabies?
2. What is the level of respondents' attitudes toward dog-bites related rabies?
3. What is the level of practices of the respondents on dog-bites related rabies?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of knowledge and their profile variables?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' knowledge and their attitudes and practices?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional research design to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of residents in Barangay Linao East, Tuguegarao City regarding dog bites, as Creswell (2014) notes that cross-sectional designs are appropriate for examining variables and their relationships at a single point in time.

Study Site of the Study. The study was conducted in Linao East, Tuguegarao City. Questionnaires were distributed to the dog owners and dog bite victims, and they were guided to complete the instrument according to the instructions.

Population, Sample, and Sampling Method. The population of this study consisted of residents of Barangay Linao East, Tuguegarao City, with particular focus on households where at least one member had experienced a dog bite. From this population, a total of 185 respondents were identified and included in the study.

The researcher employed purposive sampling to ensure that only individuals relevant to the objectives were selected. A house-to-house survey was conducted to identify households that met the inclusion criteria, and if a member had been bitten by a dog, the survey questionnaire was administered. This sampling technique was deemed appropriate as it allowed the researcher to directly target respondents with firsthand experience of dog bites, thereby ensuring that the data collected reflected the knowledge, attitudes, and practices most pertinent to rabies prevention and control.

Research Instrument. The study utilized a structured survey questionnaire as the primary research instrument for data collection. The instrument was composed of four parts designed to capture the respondents' demographic profile, knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to dog bites. Part I elicited demographic information, including date of birth, age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, primary occupation, and gross monthly family income.

Part II consisted of nine items assessing the respondents' knowledge of dog bites, measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Not at all knowledgeable) to 5 (Extremely knowledgeable). Part III contained five items evaluating attitudes toward dog bites, with responses measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

Part IV comprised seven items examining practices related to dog bites, using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Never Perform) to 5 (Always Perform). Prior to the actual data collection, the questionnaire was pretested and pilot tested among 50 participants to ensure clarity, validity, and reliability.

The reliability analysis yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.80, which indicates good internal consistency of the instrument. This result confirmed that the

questionnaire was a dependable tool for assessing the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the respondents in relation to dog bites.

Legend 1. Scoring Guide for Knowledge of the respondents on Dog bites.

Likert Scale	Mean Range	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	Extremely Knowledgeable
4	3.50-4.49	Very Knowledgeable
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Knowledgeable
2	1.50-2.49	Slight Knowledgeable
1	1.00-1.49	Not Knowledgeable

Legend 2. Scoring Guide for Attitude of the respondents on Dog bites.

Likert Scale	Mean Range	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.50-4.49	Agree
3	2.50-3.49	Neutral
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree

Legend 3. Scoring Guide for Practices of the respondents on Dog bites.

Likert Scale	Mean Range	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	Always Perform
4	3.50-4.49	Often Perform
3	2.50-3.49	Sometimes Perform
2	1.50-2.49	Rarely Perform
1	1.00-1.49	Never Perform

Data Collection. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Punong Barangay of Linao East, and informed consent was secured from all participating dog owners prior to the administration of the questionnaire. Following field validation, the survey instruments were distributed to dog owners and dog bite victims, who were guided to complete the questionnaire according to the instructions provided. For respondents who were unable to read or write, face-to-face interviews were conducted to ensure inclusivity and accuracy of responses.

Participants were allowed to raise questions for clarification, and the researcher ensured that an appropriate environment was provided while the instrument was being completed. After the questionnaires were accomplished, the researcher reviewed each instrument to verify completeness of responses. The filled-out questionnaires were then

retrieved, systematically analyzed, and carefully interpreted to generate valid findings for the study.

Data Analysis. Following data collection, the information was sorted, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using the most appropriate statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics, including weighted mean and standard deviation, were employed to summarize the responses. A Five-point Likert scale was used to interpret the levels of Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices on Dog bites.

RESULTS

The following tables present the results obtained from the analysis and interpretation of the data collected in relation to rabies knowledge, attitudes, and practices among the respondents. The study focused on several key aspects relevant to rabies prevention and control, including the level of awareness on rabies transmission, symptoms, and prevention measures; the respondents' practices during dog-related incidents; and the overall relationship between demographic variables and rabies-related knowledge and behavior. The results are organized and presented according to the specific research questions formulated in the study.

Table 1. The Level of Knowledge on Dog-Related Rabies

Parameters	WM	SD	DI
1. Rabies can be transmitted to humans through dog bites.	4.72	0.80	EK
2. The rabies virus is mainly transmitted through the saliva of infected dogs.	4.40	1.20	VK
3. Dog bites can cause injuries such as scratches, puncture wounds, deep cuts, and crush injuries.	4.74	0.69	EK
4. The first action after a dog bite is to wash the affected area with soap and running water.	4.72	0.66	EK
5. Post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) is available to prevent rabies after a dog bite.	4.15	1.71	VK
6. Dog bite incidents should be reported to authorities (LGU, DOH, or DA) within 24 hours.	4.42	1.15	VK
7. Dogs should be regularly vaccinated to prevent rabies.	4.50	1.03	EK
8. Dogs that bite someone should be placed under observation by a veterinarian.	4.55	0.93	EK
9. Pet owners should assist dog bite victims and cover medical and related expenses.	4.52	1.01	EK
Overall Mean	4.47	1.02	VK

*WM= Weighted Mean; SD= Standard Deviation; DI= Descriptive Interpretation; EK= Extremely Knowledgeable; VK = Very Knowledgeable

Table 1 presents that the respondents demonstrated a very high level of knowledge on dog-related rabies, with an overall mean of 4.47 (SD = 1.02). They showed extremely high knowledge on rabies transmission through dog bites, bite-related injuries, immediate wound care, dog vaccination, observation of biting dogs, and pet owners' responsibilities. Items on rabies transmission via saliva, post-exposure prophylaxis, and reporting bites to authorities were rated very knowledgeable, indicating areas where further education may be beneficial. These findings aligned with the study of Tuaño (2025) which emphasized that Filipino communities are becoming more familiar with rabies prevention but continue to exhibit varying levels of knowledge depending on education and socioeconomic conditions. This pattern is also reflected in a systematic review by Woldegeorgis et al. (2023), which noted generally high awareness across communities but persistent gaps in knowledge of proper post-bite management. Overall, the findings reflect strong community awareness of rabies prevention and management, with minor gaps that can be targeted for improvement.

Table 2. The Level of Attitudes on Dog-Related Rabies

Parameters	WM	SD	DI
1. I think that pet owners should be responsible in the reduction of infection brought about by dog bites between dogs and humans.	4.85	0.496	SA
2. I think that regular vaccination of pets like dogs should be observed by all pet owners to safeguard the safety of everyone including the safety of the owners.	4.85	0.491	SA
3. I think that doing specific action against even a minor animal bite is very important to prevent infections and rabies.	4.82	0.541	SA
4. I think that dog owners should follow the responsible pet ownership ordinance of the city is a must to prevent animal bites in the community.	4.87	0.435	SA
5. I think that notifying the authorities like Department of Health if bitten by a dog will help prevent the spread of rabies virus.	4.76	0.737	SA
Overall Mean	4.83	0.540	SA

*WM= Weighted Mean; SD= Standard Deviation; DI= Descriptive Interpretation; SA= Strongly Agree

Table 2 shows the respondents' level of attitude toward dog-related rabies. With an overall weighted mean of 4.83 (SD = 0.540), the respondents are Strongly Agreeing (SA) on all items, indicating a highly positive attitude. Similarly, the findings also comparable to findings from Sivagurunathan et al. (2021), who reported that communities strongly agree on the importance of responsible pet ownership, regular vaccination, and reporting bite incidents. Similarly, Iddi et al. (2023) in Tanzania found that respondents expressed a high level of agreement regarding responsible pet care and rabies prevention behaviors, mirroring the high attitude scores in this study. They recognize the importance

of pet owner responsibility, regular dog vaccination, immediate action after bites, compliance with local ordinances, and reporting to authorities as key measures to prevent rabies. Furthermore, these results suggest that the community holds a strong sense of responsibility and awareness regarding dog bite prevention and rabies control.

Table 3. The Level of Practices on Dog-Related Rabies

Parameters	WM	SD	DI
1. I wash the wound with soap and water after being bitten by a dog.	4.58	0.52	AP
2. I go to the nearest animal bite center for anti-rabies vaccination after being bitten by a dog.	4.12	1.10	OP
3. I visit a traditional healer for the “tandok” treatment.	3.18	1.82	SP
4. I wash my wounds with clean water only after being bitten by a dog.	4.28	0.96	OP
5. I use herbal medicines like garlic to treat my wound after being bitten by a dog.	3.30	2.02	SP
6. I take antibiotics after being bitten by a dog.	3.05	2.19	SP
7. I perform other practices aside from those mentioned above after being bitten by a dog.	1.50	0.72	NP
Overall Mean	3.29	1.16	SP

*WM= Weighted Mean; SD= Standard Deviation; DI= Descriptive Interpretation; AP= Always Perform; OP= Often Perform; SP= Sometimes Perform; NP=Never Perform

Table 3 presents that respondents exhibit a moderate level of practice with suggested practices after canine bites with a total mean score of 3.29 (SD = 1.16) which can be interpreted as sometimes performed. The most practiced areas are the proper wound care, in particular washing the wound with soap and water (mean = 4.58), and the following anti-rabies vaccination (mean = 4.12). On the other hand, involvement with traditional healing modalities, usage of herbal remedies, or administration of antibiotics seems to be an episodic phenomenon only and may indicate a partial or even selective dependence upon alternative or informal treatment pathways. These findings aligned with the study of Li et al. (2021) that while many animal bite victims in Central China knew appropriate wound care and vaccination protocols, a considerable number still opted for inappropriate or traditional remedies—similar to the intermittent use of “tandok,” herbal treatments, and self-medication seen among this study’s respondents. Furthermore, there is minimal deviation with respect to the standard preventive procedures as very few participants report being involved in other, less specified therapeutic practices (mean = 1.50).

Table 4. Relationship between Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices

Variable	Knowledge	Attitude	Practices
Knowledge	1.000	0.634*	0.127
Attitudes	0.634*	1.000	0.115
Practices	0.127	0.115	1.000
*Significant at 0.05			

Table 4 indicates a strong and statistically significant relationship between knowledge and attitude ($r = 0.634$, $p = -0.05$), which implies that an improved awareness of dog-related rabies has a significant impact on favorable views on rabies prevention and control. On the other hand, there was no statistical significance in relationships between knowledge and practice ($r = 0.127$) or between attitude and practice ($r = 0.115$). This trend is reflected in various rabies studies, including those by Rysava et al. (2022) and Kanda et al. (2022), which highlight structural barriers—such as limited access to animal bite treatment centers and inconsistent local surveillance systems—that prevent communities from turning awareness into consistent preventive practices. The implications of these findings are that despite the clear cognition and perceptions of the knowledgeable respondents regarding the appropriate rabies prevention and control, these cognitions do not always lead to consistent behavioral compliance, which might be due to practical reasons of convenience, lack of access to medical services, or even preference of traditional solutions.

DISCUSSION

The analysis of a data shows that the residents of Barangay Linao East have a rather good level of knowledge related to dog-related rabies. Most of them seem to understand the basics of the spread of rabies, its prevention, and emergency post-bite response. This heightened level of awareness may be largely attributed to continuing information-promotion on rabies nationwide, passage of the Anti-Rabies Act of 2007 (RA 9482), and in-service health-education programs that are initiated on a regular basis by the local health workers. However, there are still substantive misunderstandings, including the role of saliva in the spread of pathogens, the urgency of the post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP), and the appropriate process in response to a bite.

Such knowledge gaps highlight the need to employ more specific educational intervention strategies that can be used to counteract particularly the false beliefs that are still deeply rooted in the community. Within the sphere of attitudes, the results indicate that residents have a favorable and active attitude to rabies prevention and control. A significant percentage of the respondents admitted that rabies is a severe deadly condition that should be attended to as soon as possible. Respondents have also stated that they are willing to participate in community vaccination programs and follow responsible practices in owning pets. These positive attitudes are necessary, because the behavioral theory provides that positive perceptions often come before the taking of preventive measures. However, some elements of complacency could be observed among some of the respondents who believed in the fact that rabies issues are limited to

dog owners or that vaccinated dogs can no longer serve as the source of transmitting the infectious disease- the misconceptions, which may lead to the inconsistency of preventive behavior.

In terms of practice, the findings show that most households adopt proper options, including having their dogs vaccinated, keeping them locked, and going to a doctor after a dog has bitten, but the overall rates of adherence are not steady. Other families are not in compliance with the suggested yearly vaccine schedule, and some overuse homeopathic treatment or wait after being bitten. These behaviors may increase the current rabies threat in the community. The observed gaps between what people should know and what they actually do are typical of an overall behavioral pattern in the field of public health: awareness does not necessarily lead to the performance of the recommended behavior. The practices may also be affected by environmental factors such as financial constraints, accessibility of the services offered by the veterinary, and other cultural beliefs. When combined, the results regarding knowledge, attitudes, and practices assessed together, the general information and readiness of the community in the Barangay Linao East are observed to be rather high, yet the gap between the knowledge and the stable behavior will be regarded as the key issue.

Enhancing the control of rabies thus involves a long-term community involvement, better implementation of RA 9482, and alternative access to low-cost veterinary and medical care. In addition, community-based and culturally sensitive health-education programs ought to be established and launched. interventions remain essential in reinforcing accurate information, correcting misconceptions, and cultivating long-term responsible dog ownership behaviors.

Conclusions

The results show that the residents of Barangay Linao East have a rather impressive level of knowledge and a significantly favorable attitude to dog-related rabies. These members present with an awareness that cuts across the pathways of rabies spread, injuries related to bites, appropriate wound care, canine vaccination measures and the liability involved to pet owners. The translation of this knowledge, however, into regular preventive measures is moderate; a section of the population still uses traditional remedies or applies partial treatment measures.

Knowledge has a positive impact on attitudes, but neither knowledge nor attitudes had a statistically significant relationship with actual practices, meaning that the expression of behavior is dependent on other contextual or situational variables. In sum, the thesis highlights that although the presence of awareness and positive perception on the issue of rabies prevention is very evident, concrete efforts are justified to strengthen the adoption of preventive practices.

Recommendations

Considering the findings, the recommendations are as follows:

- 1. Health Education Programs:** Seminars and rabies prevention, proper wound care, and the importance of post exposures prophylaxis should be done regularly as a community-based program and this will help to reinforce knowledge and correct the misconception about the traditional treatment.
- 2. Available Medical Services:** There should be an effort to promote the accessibility and availability of anti-rabies vaccination centers and animal bite services which promote the provision of medical interventions promptly after the occurrence of a victim of dog bites.
- 3. Responsible Pet Ownership:** Local ordinances on pet vaccination and control should be encouraged and emphasized with the work of dog owners avoiding bites and the transmission of rabies.
- 4. Community Engagement:** Local leaders, barangay health workers, and schools must be actively engaged in the promotion of preventive measures in order to reduce the disconnect between the awareness and the continuity of behavior.
- 5. Surveillance and Notification:** Systems on how to report instances of dog-bite to the authorities should also be reinforced with the provision of immediate follow-up and monitoring on the biting dogs.
- 6. Future Studies:** To understand the factors that hinder the ability of residents to regularly follow the suggested rabies-prevention steps, especially dependence on the use of traditional remedies, qualitative studies should be conducted.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher made vigorous effort to protect the anonymity of all respondents and made sure that the consent to participate in data collection was free and voluntary. Data collected was strictly kept confidential, well archived and disposed of at the end of the study. Secrecy was maintained at all levels of the research process. The researcher also made every effort to prevent plagiarism, which ensured that the analysis and interpretation of findings were not biased at all. The research was conducted in full compliance with the standards of academic integrity, and all results were kept confidential, intended solely to serve academic purposes. Lastly, the researcher used artificial intelligence tools to help edit grammar and paraphrasing to make the manuscript more likely to be understood and accurate.

REFERENCES

- Constantino, C., Da Silva, E. C., Dos Santos, D. M., Paploski, I. A. D., Lopes, M. O., Morikawa, V. M., & Biondo, A. W. (2023). One Health approach on dog bites: Demographic and associated socioeconomic factors in southern Brazil. *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 8(4), 189. <https://doi.org/10.3390/tropicalmed8040189>
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

- Devira, R., Nugraha, A. D., Kurniasih, T., & Wicaksono, A. (2023). Knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding rabies among dog owners in West Java, Indonesia. *Journal of the Indonesian Veterinary Medical Association*, 4(2), 112–120. <https://doi.org/10.22146/jsv.80495>
- Iddi, S., Mlenga, F., Hamasaki, K., Mwita, S., & Konje, E. (2023). Assessment of knowledge, attitude, and practice of dog owners to rabies disease in Kahama town council, Shinyanga region, Tanzania. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 17(9), e0011580. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0011580>
- Kanda, K., Jayasinghe, A., Jayasinghe, C., & Yoshida, T. (2022). A Regional Analysis of the Progress of Current Dog-Mediated Rabies Control and Prevention. *Pathogens*, 11(10), 1130. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11101130>
- Kandel, R., Subedi, A., & Adhikari, S. (2024). Agile and reactive rabies vaccination techniques in countries with low and middle incomes. *Animal Diseases*, 4, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s44149-024-00121-2>
- Li, D., Liao, H., Chen, F., Jiang, Q., Wang, T., Lu, Z., Liu, Q., & Cao, S. (2021). The wound severity of animal bite victims visiting rabies prevention clinics and the influencing factors in Central China: A cross-sectional investigation. *BMC Public Health*, 21, 12207. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-12207-4>
- Republic Act No. 9482. (2007). Anti-Rabies Act of 2007. Government of the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2007/05/25/republic-act-no-9482/>
- Rysava, K., Espineda, J., Silo, E. A. V., Carino, S., Aringo, A. M., Bernales, R. P., Adonay, F. F., Tildesley, M. J., & Hampson, K. (2022). One Health surveillance for rabies: A case study of integrated bite case management in Albay province, Philippines. *Frontiers in Tropical Diseases*, 3, 787524. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fitd.2022.787524>
- Sivagurunathan, C., Umadevi, R., Balaji, A., Rama, R., & Gopalakrishnan, S. (2021). Knowledge, attitude, and practice study on animal bite, rabies, and its prevention in an urban community. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 10(2), 850–856. https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_1674_20
- Tuaño, R. A. (2025). KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES, AND PRACTICES IN RABIES PREVENTION AND MANAGEMENT. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15407859>
- Woldegeorgis, B. Z., Genebo, A. P., Gebrekidan, A. Y., Kassie, G. A., Azeze, G. A., & Asgedom, Y. S. (2023). Knowledge, attitudes and prevention practices related to dog-mediated rabies in Ethiopia: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational epidemiological studies from inception to 2023. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1276859>
- World Health Organization. (2023). Rabies fact sheet. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/rabies>